

Self-sensing Technology for Dynamic Behavior Analysis and Damage Classification in Rotating Rotor Blades

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[1] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tXS5St-ak7U>

Tail Rotor Blade

- Anti-torque system
- Made of CFRPs

Damages

- X High centrifugal force
- X Fatigue
- X Impact and wear

A safety-critical part [1]

- Tail rotor blades play a critical role in maintaining the helicopter's balance.
- Tail rotor blades, though essential for safety, are highly vulnerable to damage.
- It is essential to monitor the structural health of helicopter rotor blades in real-time to detect potential damage early and extend their lifespan.

1. Introduction

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 [3] W, Feng. et al., *Sustainability*, 15(18), (2023), 18783.
 [4] R, Wu. et al., *MSSP*, 130, (2019), 470-483.
 [5] Y, He. et al., *MSSP*, 219, (2024), 111592.

[6] D, Bonilla. et al., *EWSHM*, (2024)
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• Structural Health Monitoring Methods of Rotating Blades

① Strain – Image

② Visual

③ Strain - Fiber Bragg Grating

Fig. 1. Measurement setup of the offshore rotor blade.

④ Acoustic Emission(AE)

⑤ Vibration

A customized structural health monitoring technology is needed for tail rotor blades.
 → **Self-sensing** technology is well-suited for this purpose.

• Limitations

① Strain – Image

[3]

[4]

- High-speed rotation → Hard to capture stable images
- The tail rotor is small. → Difficult to capture precise images
- Operating a drone near rotating blades → Hazardous

② Visual

[5]

③ Strain - Fiber Bragg Grating

[6]

- Prone to breaking easily from pressure or impact
- Expensive and labor-intensive

Fig. 1. Measurement setup of the offshore rotor blade.

④ Acoustic Emission(AE)

[7]

- Works well on large fixed structures, but is hard to detect in environments with fast-moving and noise.

⑤ Vibration

[8]

A customized structural health monitoring technology is needed for tail rotor blades.
→ **Self-sensing** technology is well-suited for this purpose.

1. Introduction

• The Principle of Self-Sensing

Strain Applied

Damage Occurred

Electrical Resistance Changes

- Advantages** 👍
- Real-time
 - Intrinsic
 - Wide-area coverage
 - Cost-effective
 - Geometry-independent

• Current Status of Self-Sensing Research

Structural Health Monitoring

Prognostics and Health Management

• Current Research Gap & Research Idea

Although CFRP is widely used in rotating structures, self-sensing has not yet been applied to rotating components.

By leveraging self-sensing signals that capture strain variations induced by rotation, this approach can be extended to real-time monitoring of rotating components.

Research objective

- ✓ Analysis of the electromechanical behavior signals of rotating tail rotor blades
- ✓ Development of a structural health algorithm using the analyzed signals
- Real-time in-situ structural health monitoring of rotating rotor blades using electromechanical behavior data

• Testbed

✓ T-MOTOR NS14*4.8 Prop

- Length: 35.56 cm
- Weight : 10.5g
- Materials : CF(T800) + Epoxy + PMI foam
- Max RPM : 8900 RPM
- Storage Temp: -10 °C ~ 50 °C
- Clockwise specimen

✓ Electrodes

- Surface was sanded with a grinder.
- Wires were attached using silver paste to minimize contact resistance.
- Electrodes are fixed with epoxy adhesive.

✓ SunnySky V3508 High Efficiency Brushless Motor

- Voltage: 22.2 V
- Max rotating speed: 8,436 RPM

✓ Covis CSH012-06-0506 Hollow Slip Rings 6ch

- No. of CH: 6CH
- Noise: < 0.01 Ω
- Rotating Speed: Max 600RPM
- Working Life: 60M cycles

✓ Digital Multimeter Keithley 7510

- 2 Probe measurement
- Buffer mode
- Sampling frequency: 15,220 Hz

Classification Pipeline

Electrical Resistance \propto Mechanical Strain

Random Forest

Utilizing **real-time in-situ data** and **lightweight machine learning algorithms** enables **real-time in-situ structural health monitoring**.

Input

Log(X)

• Blade under Rotation

- **Blade under Rotation**

Time=0.28125 s

Surface: First principal strain, middle (1)

COMSOL Multiphysics

- Gravity
- Centrifugal Force
- Coriolis Effect

As the blade rotates, **gravity**, **centrifugal force**, and **Coriolis effect** cause strain values to differ at each position, leading to **periodic strain**.

→ Rotational frequency-based analysis enables evaluation of the structural state.

- **Damage Classification**

- Six damage types were first classified, followed by additional classification of severity for erosion and location for cracks.

- Step 1. Damage Type Classification

- 20 specimens with varying damage location and severity were used.
- To extract robust damage-type information, independent of position or severity.

3. Results _ Electromechanical behavior

- The signal exhibits **periodicity** due to the applied periodic strain.
- If damage exists in any part, **changes in flow patterns** and **mass imbalance** cause variations in strain, which are reflected in the electrical resistance.
- **Higher-order components** arise due to structural nonlinearity, with variations depending on the type of damage.

- Since the blades used in the experiment are two-bladed, the **2X harmonic is the most dominant in a healthy blade.**
- When damage occurs, the proportion of the **1X harmonic increases** due to imbalance.
- Each type of damage shows a distinct pattern in the magnitude and proportion of harmonics.

Stacked Bar Chart of Harmonics

• Step 1: Damage Type Classification

- For single RPM conditions, all damage types were classified with high accuracy.
- Even when multiple RPMs were mixed, the method maintained high accuracy, demonstrating the robustness of the signals.

< 240 RPM >

Real Class \ Predicted Class	N	T	C	LE	TE	I
N	123					
T		108				1
C	1		106			1
LE				110		3
TE		3			106	
I				1	1	104

Accuracy: 98.353%

< 480 RPM >

Real Class \ Predicted Class	N	T	C	LE	TE	I
N	106					
T		127				
C			113		1	
LE				95		3
TE					123	
I						118

Accuracy: 99.417%

< 360 RPM >

Real Class \ Predicted Class	N	T	C	LE	TE	I
N	130					
T		96				
C			111			1
LE				107		1
TE					122	
I	1	1	2	1		113

Accuracy: 98.980%

< RPM Mixed >

Real Class \ Predicted Class	N	T	C	LE	TE	I
N	375		1			
T	1	320	1	1		
C			326			1
LE	4	1	1	321	1	5
TE		2		1	335	
I	6	5	4		1	327

Accuracy: 98.235%

- Step 2: Damage Severity Assessment

Leading Edge Erosion (LE)

< 240 RPM >

Accuracy: 100%

< 360 RPM >

Accuracy: 99.711%

< 480 RPM >

Accuracy : 100%

< RPM Mixed >

Accuracy : 99.603%

Trailing Edge Erosion (TE)

Accuracy: 100%

Accuracy: 99.702%

Accuracy : 99.702%

Accuracy : 99.702%

- Step 2: Damage Localization**

Crack (C)

Leading Edge

Inner(LI)

Middle(LM)

Outer(LO)

Trailing Edge

Inner(TI)

Middle(TM)

Outer(TO)

The high accuracy in both damage severity and localization further demonstrates the robustness of self-sensing technology.

Accuracy: 98.83%

Accuracy: 97.368%

Accuracy : 98.830%

Accuracy : 98.538%

- **Importance**

- Harmonics at multiples of six are generally found to be the most significant.
- The harmonics considered important vary depending on the classification target.
- This reveals how each type of damage affects different harmonic components.

- **Conclusions**

- ✓ **Real-time Monitoring:** The self-sensing technology successfully enabled real-time structural health monitoring of rotating rotor blades by leveraging the piezoresistive properties of CFRPs.
- ✓ **High Accuracy:** The approach demonstrated high classification accuracy in identifying damage types, severity levels, and locations under various rotational conditions.
- ✓ **Improved Safety and Efficiency:** This method offers a significant improvement over traditional systems, enhancing flight safety and reducing maintenance costs through continuous real-time monitoring.

- **Future Work**

- ✓ Investigation of the correlation between higher-order harmonics based on rotational frequencies and damage signatures
- ✓ Quantitative damage assessment

Thank You For Listening

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